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METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO HOUSING CONSTRUCTION DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN: INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY AND PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP MECHANISMS

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Abstract. This article examines methodological approaches to the development of housing construction in Uzbekistan under conditions of rapid urbanization and increasing housing demand. Particular attention is paid to investment efficiency and public-private partnership mechanisms. Based on an analysis of current trends in the construction industry and housing stock development, the key factors affecting the efficiency of housing construction are identified. The study proposes directions for improving the housing construction management system aimed at ensuring sustainable sectoral development and increasing housing accessibility.

Keywords: housing construction, housing stock, investment, public-private partnership, construction industry, efficiency, Uzbekistan.

Аннотация. В статье исследуются методологические подходы к развитию жилищного строительства в Узбекистане в условиях активной урбанизации и роста потребности населения в жилье. Особое внимание уделяется вопросам повышения инвестиционной эффективности и использования механизмов государственно-частного партнерства. На основе анализа современных тенденций развития строительной отрасли и жилищного фонда выявлены ключевые факторы, влияющие на эффективность жилищного строительства. Предложены направления совершенствования системы управления жилищным строительством, направленные на обеспечение устойчивого развития отрасли и повышение доступности жилья.

Ключевые слова: жилищное строительство, жилищный фонд, инвестиции, государственно-частное партнерство, строительная отрасль, эффективность, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

Housing construction is one of the most important sectors of the national economy, as it directly affects living standards, employment, investment activity, and urban development. In recent years, Uzbekistan has implemented large-scale reforms aimed at expanding housing availability and improving construction infrastructure. As a result, the housing stock reached 703.8 million square meters in 2025, increasing by approximately 1.3 times compared to 2021 [1].

The rapid growth of the housing sector has been accompanied by an increase in construction activity. According to official statistics, the volume of construction works performed in Uzbekistan reached 233.8 trillion soums in 2024, demonstrating steady growth compared to previous years [2]. At the same time, more than 2,000 multi-apartment residential buildings were commissioned in 2024, providing housing for over 100,000 families [3].

Despite these positive developments, several challenges remain. These include the need to improve investment efficiency, optimize the use of financial resources, and strengthen cooperation between public authorities and private investors. In this regard, methodological approaches based on investment management and public-private partnership (PPP) mechanisms are becoming increasingly important.

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to assess the current state of housing construction development in Uzbekistan and identify methodological directions for improving investment efficiency and PPP-based housing development mechanisms.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Foreign scholars have extensively investigated housing construction and public-private partnership mechanisms. Batra emphasized that PPP models contribute to efficient risk allocation and improve stakeholder cooperation in housing projects. Moreover, the author identified institutional support and governance quality as key determinants of successful housing programs [4]. Building on these findings, recent international studies increasingly focus on integrating investment efficiency with sustainable housing development strategies.

In the CIS and Russian scientific literature, significant attention has been paid to investment management in construction projects. Researchers such as Konyev and Dolgalova argue that PPP mechanisms facilitate the attraction of private capital while reducing fiscal pressure on governments. Their studies demonstrate that long-term cooperation between the public and private sectors improves project sustainability and infrastructure quality [5]. Consequently, PPP has become one of the most widely discussed instruments of modern housing policy.

In Uzbekistan, housing construction development has been analyzed by Mirisaev, Rajapov, and Davletov. Their research highlights the importance of investment evaluation methods, mortgage financing systems, and economic modeling tools for forecasting housing demand and optimizing construction volumes [6, 7]. Nevertheless, the issue of developing an integrated methodological framework that combines investment efficiency assessment with PPP mechanisms remains insufficiently explored.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employs comparative, analytical, and statistical research methods. Scientific publications, official statistical reports, and analytical materials related to the development of housing construction were examined.

The methodological framework includes:

- comparative analysis of national and international approaches;
- assessment of housing stock development indicators;
- analysis of construction sector performance;
- evaluation of investment efficiency factors;
- synthesis of PPP development mechanisms.

The study also applies trend analysis to identify the dynamics of housing construction development in Uzbekistan.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis of statistical data indicates that housing construction has become one of the most dynamically developing sectors of Uzbekistan's economy. During the period under review, the country implemented a number of reforms aimed at increasing housing affordability, attracting private investment, and expanding the participation of business entities in the construction sector. These measures contributed to a significant increase in the volume of commissioned housing and the overall housing stock.

According to official statistics, the total housing stock in Uzbekistan increased from 549.0 million square meters in 2021 to 703.8 million square meters in 2025. This growth demonstrates the positive impact of state housing programs, favorable mortgage financing mechanisms, and increased investment activity in the construction industry. At the same time, the housing sector remains one of the key instruments for improving living standards and ensuring sustainable socio-economic development [8] (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of Housing Stock Development in Uzbekistan, 2021–2025¹

¹ Compiled by the author

The figure clearly demonstrates a stable upward trend in housing development. The growth rate remained positive throughout the period, confirming the resilience of the construction sector despite uncertainties in the global economic environment. This finding supports the conclusions of Batra, who argued that sustainable housing development largely depends on effective cooperation between public authorities and private stakeholders [9].

Another important finding concerns the role of public–private partnership mechanisms in housing development. International experience shows that PPP projects contribute to the mobilization of financial resources, risk sharing, and improvement of project management efficiency [10]. In Uzbekistan, the gradual introduction of PPP principles in infrastructure and residential projects creates additional opportunities for attracting long-term private investment while reducing the financial burden on the state budget.

The results also indicate that investment efficiency remains one of the determining factors of housing sector performance. Studies emphasize that effective assessment of investment projects allows for better resource allocation and contributes to the sustainability of construction activities (Table 1).

Table 1
Main Indicators Characterizing Housing Stock Development in Uzbekistan²

Year	Housing stock (million m ²)	Absolute increase (million m ²)	Growth rate (%)
2021	549.0	-	-
2022	636.4	87.4	15.9
2023	658.4	22.0	3.5
2024	692.5	34.1	5.2
2025	703.8	11.3	1.6

As shown in Table 1, the housing stock in Uzbekistan demonstrated stable growth throughout the study period. The highest growth rate was observed in 2022, when the housing stock increased by 15.9% compared to the previous year. This significant increase was associated with the implementation of large-scale housing programs and the expansion of mortgage financing opportunities. In subsequent years, growth continued at a more moderate pace, indicating the transition of the housing sector toward sustainable and balanced development. By 2025, the housing stock reached 703.8 million square meters, which was approximately 28.2% higher than in 2021 [11].

The observed dynamics are closely related to the expansion of investment flows into the construction industry. The increasing involvement of private investors, commercial banks, and development companies has contributed to the implementation of large-scale residential projects. Moreover, the government has introduced a number of institutional reforms aimed at simplifying construction procedures and improving access to financial resources.

The findings suggest that further improvement of housing construction development in Uzbekistan should be based on three interrelated directions. First, mechanisms for attracting private investment through PPP arrangements should be strengthened. Second, modern investment evaluation tools should be incorporated into housing policy decision-making processes. Third, digital technologies and forecasting models should be used to improve planning efficiency and optimize resource allocation [12].

Therefore, the combination of investment efficiency assessment, public–private partnership mechanisms, and strategic planning tools can create favorable conditions for the sustainable development of the housing sector. The implementation of these approaches may enhance housing affordability, improve construction quality, and strengthen the overall competitiveness of the national construction industry [13].

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study confirmed that housing construction plays an important role in the socio-economic development of Uzbekistan and contributes to improving living standards. The analysis showed a steady increase in the housing stock and the growing importance of investment activity in the construction sector.

The findings indicate that improving housing construction development requires the wider application of public–private partnership (PPP) mechanisms, enhancement of investment efficiency assessment methods, and the use of modern planning tools. The implementation of these measures will contribute to increasing

² Compiled by the author

housing accessibility, attracting private investment, and ensuring the sustainable development of the housing sector in Uzbekistan.

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